

Adaptation of the Seam Carving Technique for Improving Audio Time-Scaling

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Master Thesis submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the degree:

Master en Tecnologies de la Informació, la Comunicació i els Mitjans Audiovisuals

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September 2008

This paper is the Master Thesis of the TICMA Master (Tecnologies de la Informació i la Comunicació en Mitjans Audiovisuals) from MTG (Musical Technology Group) at UPF (Universitat Pompeu Fabra). This project represents an important subject of the course and it reflects some research in a topic and the application of some knowledge given during this course. In this paper the author explains in detail his Master Thesis and the expected results using the described methodologies. The tutor of this Master Thesis has been Jordi Janer, a member of MTG at UPF

ABOUT THE AUTHOR

The author is graduated in Enginyeria Superior en Telecomunicacions, which included courses on signal processing using Matlab. One of the projects implemented during this bachelor was [4], and the other was a second layer implementation of the Galileo's communication earth-satellite using WCDMA (wideband code division multiple access), called "Anàlisi de l'adquisició del senyal de telemetria del sistema Galileo" and implemented in Matlab too. This Master Thesis is the last subject of the author while enrolling a master program in information, communication and audiovisual media technologies (TICMA), which is largely related with the previous projects during the bachelor.

The author combined the TICMA Master course with his job at Triple Onda, leading the R+D Department and designing professional cabinets for professional applications. Also, he combined engineering tasks with Saturday nights on a Discothèque. All this experience and work will converge in a PhD Thesis.

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Abstract

This Master Thesis addresses the topic of adapting the Seam Carving Algorithm, an Image Processing Technique (IPT), for an audio Time-Scale application. We adapt an image-resizing algorithm for analyzing spectrograms images, which represent audio information. This approach aims to improve certain limitations of an existing Time Scale algorithm. The current Time-Scale Algorithm produces some sound artifacts when there is a slow audio attack and a large time-scale factor is applied. We suggest that using Seam Carving Algorithm some improvements could be achieved due to a bigger and customized analysis window than the Time-Scale Algorithm. Basically, we assume that a window with low energy of transients can be time-scaled without artifacts and, contrary, we must keep the duration of zones with high energy of transients. Using IPT we can obtain some results that are not possible using only classical Audio Processing Techniques. For instance, analyzing the Spectrogram using IPT can analyze long-term patterns difficult to detect in the Short-Term Fourier Transform (STFT). This method splits first the audio signal based on rhythm information. The Seam Carving Algorithm is applied to each window of the spectrogram images resulting from the segmentation, generating an envelope of varying time-scaling factors. From the results, we argue that with the appropriate analysis parameters, we improve the transformation quality. Also, we observed that the rhythm-based segmentation is crucial, so that a user-supervised process will be useful.

Index Terms

Audio Manipulation, Audio Processing, Image Processing Techniques, Attack and Delay Preservation, Seam Carving, Spectrogram, STFT, Time Scale, Time Stretch.

I. INTRODUCTION

This paper is the Master Thesis Project of the TICMA Master (Tecnologies de la Informació i la Comunicació dels Mitjans Audiovisuals) at Universitat Pompeu Fabra (UPF).

This Master Thesis Project is an adaptation of the Seam Carving Algorithm [2] for Spectrograms, which is applied as a pre-processing of a current Time-Scale Algorithm designed by Jordi Bonada [1]. This new method was proposed by Jordi Bonada and Jordi Janer, both members of the MTG, in order to improve an existing Time-Scale algorithm [1], which has some problems for detecting slow transients due to a small window decision. In this Master Thesis, our goal is to improve the results by using a bigger window analysis for deciding high and low energy of transients. In addition, we think that it is possible because is not the same to find some properties in a sound using the common audio techniques, like time domain or frequency domain techniques, than using IPT (Image Processing techniques). It must be clear that the algorithm we have designed only uses audio information for extracting the tempo and the energy of the transients in each window, but it doesn't transforms the audio file. All the audio transformations are done by the original algorithm designed by Jordi Bonada, using a time scale curve, extracted from the algorithm we are describing. A different approach would be to make transformations directly on the spectrogram, but this is beyond our initial scope.

Therefore, this project has the objective of describing the modifications of the initial seam carving algorithm in order to be useful for spectrograms and design a new way to convert all the seams removed over spectrograms to a time-scale factor envelope function to be used with the Time-Scale Algorithm.

First, this Master Thesis Project describes briefly some literature about achieving audio transformations based on image-processing techniques. Then, we describe in detail all the methodology by adapting the original seam-carving algorithm for image-resizing to seam carving for spectrograms and its application to Time-Scaling. Finally, some results and conclusions are described showing how this method works and which are the improvements and differences with the previous work.

II. OBJECTIVES

The Seam Carving algorithm [2] is an innovative content-aware image processing technique for image-resizing. It is based in generate an energy map for both axis (x,y) and find the minimum seam over an axis. Since we are using it for finding transients in time, we only need the time dimension (x axis) of the algorithm. The other dimension (y axis) is the frequency domain representation of the audio file in a spectrogram. It implies a reduction of the complexity of the algorithm. We must take into account that all the analysis will be over an image, a spectrogram containing audio information. A synthesis algorithm is not implemented. In order to apply the time-scale function, we generate a time-scale factor envelope as a breakpoint function. The existing Time-Scale Algorithm [1] will process all the audio transformations of the original audio file. This algorithm operates in stereo and mono mode with the same time-scale factor envelope function.

As a preliminary step, in order to keep the tempo of the file and avoid to detect many seams in the same area of the file (such silences), we need to design an onset time detection algorithm to decide the length of the spectrogram image to be computed by the seam-carving for spectrograms algorithm. It means that the spectrogram will represent a portion of the audio file. From the beginning to the end of this portion in time will be referred to as a region in this project. The algorithm will find many seams over each spectrogram, which represents a region of the audio file and, finally, we must sort the seams founded and uniform it as a time-scale factor envelope. The next step it to filter this function obtaining a smooth time-scale factor envelope function in order to avoid fast transitions on the time-scale factor envelope. The mean of this time-scale factor envelope function must be the time-scale factor the user applies and the transients of this curve will be slower. This time-scale factor envelope will be the result of compressing or expanding the horizontal axis, the time in a spectrogram. The vertical axis is the resolution of the FFT, the window size as an input for the FFT. Finally, the third dimension will be the amplitude or energy of the signal over these two dimensions (the pixel value in an image).

Once we have an image, it will be the input of the seam-carving algorithm. We will

explain how we have adapted the algorithm for finding seams over the time dimension. When it detects successfully the transients, we must save all the seams removed in order to make it as the input of the Time-Scale Algorithm. The Time-Scale Algorithm reads a text file containing the time-scale factor envelope function over a specific defined region. We design this text file with as many regions as we want. In this way, each region will coincide with each seam removed.

As the seam-carving authors [2] explain, this algorithm is useful to reduce or increase the dimension of a picture maintaining the most important features untouchables. In the same way, we can reduce or increase the duration of the audio file, by determining positive (expansion) or negative (compression) time-scale factors.

Finally, a perceptual experiment for evaluation is carried out in order to compare the results of this method with other methods, like the original time-scale algorithm [1] and state if there is some improvement and which new features with this new proposal. We cannot forget that there is no objective or analytic way to determine which algorithm is better. Therefore, the best is the one that sounds better for more people.

III. BRIEF REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

Next, we review the State-of-the-art of the current Audio Synthesis (AS) based on Image Processing Techniques (IPT). Several Systems use images for synthesizing sounds or generating some transformations on an audio file. There are many projects that show how to resynthesize symbolic images [7], [8], [18] to make sounds or transformations on the spectrogram and then resynthesize it as an audio process substitution.

A. Examples of resynthesizing symbol images

Woon [7] shows on his web many symbolic images in gray scale that represents some types of waves. The aim of his work is to sound some kind of images. He shows many examples which are a combination of black and white. He defines the intensity as the power of the sinusoid. The y axis are the time and the x axis are the frequency. So, the first image is a constant sinusoid on some frequency (close to the maximum frequency because the black band is on the right corner) and the second image is a pulse frequency modulation, a sinusoid that change its frequency from the minim value to the maximum value across the y axis. There are more complex textures that define PWM, FWM, etc. See figure 1.

Figure 1: each pictures defines some shape of wave. A: sine wave, B: pulse frequency modulation (1Hz), C: effects of visual filters).

MetaSynth [8] is an application that lets the user to draw audio shapes as the user wants with some patterns proposed and then resynthesize it. It is designed to create new sounds for musicians, composers, and sound designers.

The vOICe Interactive Visual Sound Applet [18] is an applet that interprets images in three dimensions. The vertical axis of an image defines the pitch (lower pitch on the bottom and higher pitch on the top), the intensity of each pixel is the loudness and the x axis corresponding a stereo-panning. In this way, one can visualize an image only interpreting what is hearing. It is such a visual sound application. See Figure 2 for many examples from the web.

Figure 2: each pictures are intended to be interpreted as a sound by the vOICe Interactive Visual Sound Applet.

B. Examples of spectrograms modification using IPT

Synthbilder [9] is a software that allows the user to transform an audio signal into a sonogram image and vice versa. It works different than the previous ones because in this case the image is a spectrogram, not a symbol sound according to the image. It means that it permits the study and examination of the conversion of digital audio signals from the time domain into the frequency domain and back again. Additionally, SynthBilder shows the utility of windowing the signal in order to extract the information we want more accurate. Finally, figure 3 shows the aspect of this software.

Figure 3: Synthbilder.

CUBE 2 - Spectral Morphing Resynthesizer [11] is a musical instrument or a tool for analyzing all principal components of a sound. This tool allows the user to analyze the sinusoidal (harmonical spectrum) and residual (inharmonical spectrum) components of the spectrum in an independent way. In addition, the user can visualize the pan spectrum for the spatial character of a sound, the phase spectrum for analyzing differences between channels. In these spectrum representations, the user can modify the spectral components in his/her own way by drawing with some available tools. Finally, some functions are available for analyzing and transformation of sounds, like resynthesis from spectrums, time warping, morphing, source editing, arpeggiator, effects, interfaces. See figure 4 for a preview of this software.

Figure 4: Cube 2 - Spectral Morphing Resynthesizer.

Sound 2D Warper [3] software is an application that works on the spectrum image from a sound following some transformation parameters. The user can apply to the spectrogram geometric transformations such as enlargement, reduction, and rotation. Essentially, this applications shows the spectrogram of a sound and then, the user can transform this sound taking a visual sampler before apply the transformations to this sound. In an easy manner, the spectrogram is only a tool to see which transformations we want to apply to the sound. Finally, when the user wants to synthesize these transformations, the program gets the parameters marked on the spectrogram and the spectrum representation of this new sound must be the same than the one we have

transformed. See figure 5 to see these geometric transformation, made by us as an illustration for this project.

These examples have the aim of showing that there are several research projects combining audio and image techniques in order to obtain new results. This is only a brief literature about techniques close to Seam Carving for Spectrograms, the proposal of this Master Thesis. In section IV we will see how to combine both techniques in order to obtain a new result: try to improve the current time-scaling algorithm with this new technique.

IV. METHODOLOGY

In this section, we describe, in detail, the process of the original seam-carving algorithm. All the transformations have been designed in order to obtain a specific output useful as an input of the time-scale algorithm [1]. Therefore, the output of our system will be a text file which include many regions with some calculated time-scale factor. All this information must be seen as a time-scale factor envelope function from the Seam Carving for Spectrograms algorithm. Each region corresponds with the time window used in the main algorithm. Usually, this region is a sixteenth of the tempo of the audio file in order to preserve the original tempo and, in an easy way, the user can calculate how many regions will have this time-scale envelope function. Moreover, actually, the user cannot predict this envelope manually, the user needs a sophisticated algorithm to calculate it. Let us see, first, the previous steps needed before redesign the Seam Carving algorithm. Second, we will see all the transformations done in this algorithm. Finally, we will see how to get and understand the output of the global system in order to determine, in an easy manner, the time-scale factor envelope function. This function is the one used by the time-scale algorithm and get transformed sounds. Then, expert subjects will compare the results of our algorithm with other program ones.

Figure 5: Sound 2D Warper 1.1 example representation of a geometric transformation on the spectrum from a sound and then the spectrogram of this new resynthesized sound fits with the one the user has drawn.

A. Introduction

First, we describe how seam-carving algorithm works in the image processing domain. We have to learn all the steps needed for finding low energy seams in an image over the vertical direction, which corresponds to a region of the sound. This image has the same size in height as the window used for analyzing the spectrogram of the audio file using the FFT. The weight of this image corresponds to the number of FFT windows we need to have a proportional region of the tempo, usually a sixteenth region of the tempo, what means that we use 4 regions per beat. This region will be determined by the overlapping the user applies. Then, we justify the modification of some parts of the original algorithm to find which zones of the spectrogram have low energy regions. It means that we must generate a horizontal gradient and choose the correct parameters for finding attacks and reduce the transitions in this gradient for the decay regions. Therefore, we must define, previously, what we understand for a low energy region. If we compute a horizontal gradient to a spectrogram, we will have some regions with many transitions and other with less transitions (we understand transition as changes in the intensity of the pixels in this direction of a given region, which is the frequency axis of each FFT window computed to draw the spectrogram). If we accumulate all the variations in a bottom-up direction, we can draw an energy map showing which regions or regions have more transitions in a defined region. It means that we have to design one way to find this low energy regions preserving the attack bands and stretching only the more irrelevant regions, the release ones, for example. Then, once we have found all the regions we can stretch, we must take into account that is not the same the compression than the expansion. In an image, compression means that we remove a seam and the picture changes his size, but there are no other problems. We must add that remove a seam is the same as removing a column in the image, but the column position of every row of the seam is not always the same like removing literally a column, which is removing the same column position for each row. If we remove so many seams, then the dimensions of the picture not allows us to understand this picture as a real image, so it becomes as unreal, but we can understand it if the compression ratio is not so high. The same argument we apply for expansion, what is

the same as compression but adding seams calculating the mean between the previous and the next pixel of any position of the seam. In addition, we cannot forget that high ratios of compression/expansion generate visible artifacts. In case that we are using spectrograms for determining low transients energy regions in a gradient image, and not low energy seams, like the original seam-carving algorithm (computationally is the same, but not conceptually), we cannot remove seams as we remove regions (FFT windows) in the audio file, because it is not stretching, it is cutting an audio file. Therefore, what we must do it to take into account that the time-scale factor cannot be zero for compression and infinite for expansion, because it means cut and duplicate infinite times, respectively. What we can do to apply some high time-scale factor on a selected region is to apply, to the previous and next regions, some low time-scale factor in order to have the time-scale factor desired not in one region, but in 3, 5, 7, etc regions (the ones that are close to the selected region). This operation is a low pas filter over the time-scaling factor envelope function. In this way, we can stretch some fragment of the audio file with good results.

Compress and expand an image is the same like audio, but knowing that the neutral time-scale factor is one. In an image we remove/duplicate pixels and in an audio file we remove/duplicate audio frames. If we want to compress we use a time-scale factor lower than 1 and the inverse respect 1 for expansion. During the computation of this algorithm, the time-scale factor of each window will be calculated and stored one time-scale factor behind the previous one constructing the output of the time-scale factor envelope function.

Also, we realized that we cannot remove as many seams as we want for determining low energy regions, instead of preserving the tempo, because, then, on the contrary thanwith the image, the audio file (music, for example) tends to change the rhythm, which is an unwanted effect. With images, a strange shape of the images are produced as artifacts. One solution is to fix a maximum seams to remove (maximum regions to remove) and then, if we need to remove more seams that the maximum, we remove the regions with less energy in order to have a histogram which sums the same seams removed as we want. It is obviously that with this method, high time-scale factors produce artifacts, but it allows maintaining the rhythm and tempo with the time-scale

factor that this algorithm has been designed:

- compression: from 0,5 to 1
- expansion: from 1 to 2

The block diagram in figure 6 shows the steps we must follow and a little description about each one to start explaining with more detail the fourth parts of this algorithm:

- how does seam-carving work?
- onset detection segmentation
- adapting seam-carving for spectrograms
- generate the time-scale envelope function into a text file for time-scale algorithm

Figure 6: Block diagram of the seam-carving for spectrograms. There is a comparison with this method and the previous one in order to compare the results and determine if this new method improves the results with the ones that the previous version produces some artifacts in the sound.

As we see in the above block diagram, the input will be almost always a mono audio file. In order to simplify the computational cost mixing the two channels of an original stereo file, we will mix both channels of the audio file, if it is stereo. In addition, we can resample this audio file to a 22050Hz of sampling frequency, because the highest bands of the audio file are usually, if not always, irrelevant for determining the tempo and transition regions. In addition, filtering the highest bands, we reduce the noise present in the file and the accumulated energy in each region will be more accurate to the highest relevant information of the file, with corresponds to low and medium bands. The time-scale algorithm applies the same time-scale factor for each channel. Then, in order to

preserve the tempo, we must calculate the tempo of the file using an onset detection algorithm and decide the duration of each window, which will be one of the size of the spectrogram image. One good window length is a sixteenth or thirty-second length of the tempo. It can be modified depending on the rhythm of the audio file. We have tried with bigger regions than sixteenth and appear artifacts with the rhythm, because tends to change. If we use a constant time region, we recommend using sixteenth length of tempo, because it is usually the minimum duration note of modern music. Also, we think this time region segmentation will avoid important changes in the rhythm. In addition, we have seen, at the end of this project that if the reader wants a high quality result, he/she must assist the algorithm defining manually the regions to be segmented. It means that the algorithm can not use higher regions as sixteenth because then there are changes in the rhythm. But, if the reader segments manually each region of the audio file, then he/she can avoid the onset detection algorithm and calculate directly the seam carving algorithm for spectrograms. The reader must take into account that as bigger is the region, better is the segmentation between high and low region in a spectrogram. Imagine that if we use only an eighth region of the tempo in a reggaeton rhythm and we apply the maximum time-scale factor compression, the rhythm will be completely different, because the time between the kick and snare will seem to be eighth duration, instead of sixteenth, which is the case. One solution is alternate between eighth and sixteenth region windows and the reader will get successful results without artifacts in the rhythm and knowing that it is not recommended to use bigger regions in order to segmentate the energy regions in the spectrogram, like attack and release regions. In this way the reader is forcing the algorithm to preserve attack regions and stretch release regions for every window segmentation the user has defined.

The next step is to calculate the spectrogram. We must design an algorithm that has enough frequency resolution to find long seams going from the low frequency bands to the highest frequency bands (bottom-up direction). One can think that the frequency resolution is not important because we are not analyzing the frequency components, but if it is low, then the seam tends to pass between the same time regions some times, and it produced poor time resolution. On the other hand, high frequency resolution is desired, but then the image tends to grow and the time for computing grows

considerably, too. Once we have the spectrogram image, we forget the audio file and all the features related to audio and we will work only over this image (one for each sixteenth or thirty-second of the tempo, multiplied for the number of beats of the audio file), using image-processing techniques. Using this spectrogram for each sixteenth or thirty-second regions, we will compute the energy map for finding low energy regions and remove the seams in this image. Once we have all the seams we want to remove, we must generate a histogram containing how many seams we want to remove for each region or window. This way, we can calculate an envelope curve for the time-scale algorithm showing the time-scale factor for each region. Finally, the output of our system will be a time-scale factor envelope function which determines the time-scale factor for each sixteenth or thirty-second region of the audio file. All this information is written in a text file, containing the number of regions to calculate and the time-scale factor at the beginning and at the end of each region to be calculated.

For applying the time-scale factor envelope function to the sound we are computing, we have, from one hand, the text file generated with the Seam Carving for Spectrograms algorithm and, from the other hand, the original audio file. The output is a new stretched audio file.

Finally, we will compare our results with the original time-scale algorithm with a constant time-scale factor and the Melodyne program.

B. How does Seam Carving work?

Seam-Carving [2] is a content-aware Image-resizing technique. It works reducing or expanding images by finding seams from top to bottom or left to right over an image energy function. It always searches for an optimal seam, the one that accumulates minimum energy in each iteration. It is the same process while reducing or expanding. The difference is that when we reduce, we delete a seam and, when we expand, we add a seam, making a mean with the previous and the next seam where the one is added. Doing it repeatedly we change the size of the image. This method protects the content of the image, as defined by the energy function. This method is applied, also, for object removal and image content enhancement. This method allows an input to protect some area or to delete it before other areas of the image. This method differs of other classical

resizing methods, like crop, column delete or pixel removal by preserve the content of the image.

These features are needed for our application, where the content of the spectrogram is important. Now, someone may think that this application can be reduced by making a spectrogram, apply the original seam-carving for the time axis and then resynthesize it to a sound by the inverse Fourier Transform. It could be a possible solution. Nevertheless, what does it happen with this option? Why was this option discarded? The answer is that when we generate a spectrogram as an image of 8 bits (gray scale) we are losing amplitude resolution. However, we can work with 16 bits resolution. Ok. Nevertheless, what does it happen with the phase when a seam is removed or added? It should be necessary to generate a phase spectrogram and calculate the phase for each seam removed or added in order to resynthesize it. Therefore, it means that it is the same as delete or replicate some audio regions in the audio file. No stretching function is used. So, the result could generate a lot of artifacts. In addition, this method does not take into account the tempo and rhythm of the audio file. For these reasons, some other technique must be applied. Figure 7 is an example of an ideal sound, which is a sinusoid, where has the minimum seam in the middle and no tempo is required for this sound. We have used this spectrogram with the original seam carving and the result is what the reader sees in figure 7. It shows that if the minimum seam is in the middle of the spectrogram, where there is not variation of the amplitude in this region, all the seams will be added or removed from this position. In figure 7, we have expanded the sinusoid as a time scale factor equal to 2, and graphically the result is good, because the attack and release region are the same as the original sound. If the rhythm is important for our application, we must design an algorithm for getting the same features as a results but with every onset. So, in figure 7, no rhythm is present and sound is well processed. But this type of sounds are not the aim of this project, because this example is only a little piece of the amount of work needed to be useful for any audio/music file.

Figure 7: on the left a STFT spectrogram of a sinusoid. On the right the time-scaled spectrogram using seam carving of a sinusoid

Let us define with more detail how this method works. This method is based on the entropy of each dimension of an image (horizontal and vertical) to find which regions of the image has high entropy from the beginning of one of the dimensions to the end of it, and the same for the other dimension. An image gradient function is used to determine the entropy of each dimension. So, seam carving can be understood as an operator, which finds these regions. The seam carving as an operator can be defined as this gradient function (equation 1), taken from the original paper [2] in order to understand this project, where e is the energy of the image and I is the image.

$$e(I) = \left| \frac{\partial}{\partial x} I \right| + \left| \frac{\partial}{\partial y} I \right|$$

Equation 1: Energy function of the I image in each direction.

For constructing the image energy function from this gradient image, we must take the first row and calculate the minimum value. Then, we must iterate from the second row to the last row searching for the minimum pixel value between the related pixels over the previous row. See equation 2 in order to see how we calculate this function, where M is the minimum energy map and e is the energy of this pixel. The sub index i represents the position over the x dimension and j the sub index over the y dimension; typically, x dimension is the horizontal and y dimension the vertical one. The same process for the other dimension, but we only consider time dimension (y dimension or vertical dimension).

$$M(i, j) = e(i, j) + \min(M(i-1, j-1), M(i-1, j), M(i-1, j+1))$$

Equation 2: Minimum energy map function of the I image, taken from the original algorithm [2], useful for both dimensions separately.

Let us see the energy function of a spectrogram image from a little fragment of a generic song. See figure 8.

Figure 8: on the right we see the spectrogram, with a window length=1024 and overlapping=1/16 from a beat of a song (100bpm) which contains first the kick, in the middle the high hat and ant the end the beginning of the snare which determines the rhythm and the vertical energy accumulations. In addition, there are some notes added in the horizontal axis. In the middle, the horizontal gradient of the spectrogram on the left. In this image we can see how the attacks has considerably higher energy than low energy regions than the spectrogram. It means that the contrast between high and low regions are higher. On the left, we see the energy map of the horizontal gradient in the middle, which contains a high energy accumulation of three instruments, kick, close hi-hat and the snare drum. The lowest seam is before the close hi-hat and the kick drum, as anyone perceives from the spectrogram and gradient image.

Once we have calculated the image energy function, we apply equation 3 in order to find the desired seams. In this project, we only need the horizontal seams, but we show how to calculate seams en both directions. Equation 3a shows how to calculate the horizontal seam from left to right and equation 3b the vertical seam from top to bottom.

Both equations 3a and 3b are taken from [2].

$$\begin{aligned}
 s^y &= \{s_j^y\}_{j=1}^m = \{(j, y(j))\}_{j=1}^m, \\
 s.t. \forall j &|y(j) - y(j-1)| \leq 1 \\
 \\
 s^x &= \{s_i^x\}_{i=1}^n = \{(x(i), i)\}_{i=1}^n, \\
 s.t. \forall i &|x(i) - x(i-1)| \leq 1
 \end{aligned}$$

Equation 3a: searching for the seam over the horizontal axis.

Equation 3b: searching for the seam over the vertical axis.

Equations 3a and 3b mean that, for example for the vertical seams, we search for the minimum pixel value in the bottom row and then look in the above row for the minimum pixel value between the one that is in the same column and the ones that are immediately on the left or on the right of it. The same operation must be done until the upper row.

At least, we will have some seam cost, which defines some threshold for defining regions. We can find it with equation 4, where the calculated seam represents the minimum accumulation of energy in this direction and iteration. Horizontal and vertical seams are calculated independently in an alternate way, one after the other and in each iteration. Equation 4 is taken from [2], too, where s is the seam, $E(s)$ the accumulated energy function and e the energy of each pixel in I over the vertical axis.

$$s^* = \min_s E(s) = \min_s \sum_{i=1}^n e(I(s_i))$$

Equation 4: the calculated seam is the sum of the minimum path over a dimension.

These operations (from equation 1 to 4) are required for each seam removed in each direction (vertical and horizontal). If we resize the image in each directions, we must alternate between horizontal and vertical until one dimension has finished. Then, we compute the other dimension until the end. It is important to consider it because, if not,

the energy map does not fit with the image content and the energy function loses sense.

Figure 8 shows us the shape of the spectrogram of a region of a polyphonic file, the horizontal gradient which is useful for getting the energy map. Then we will explain in more detail how to get each representation.

Let us see an example, from a spectrogram image, if we try to detect, with the same energy function, more than one seam. The effect is that each seam starts from a different pixel, but all of them end to the same pixel because for each iteration, each seam finds for the minimum energy path. That is one of the reasons that the energy map must be calculated after each seam removed in each dimension. See figure 9.

Figure 9: here we have a region of the spectrogram where we are finding the 1000 best seams of this energy map. What occurs is that despite that each seam starts from a different pixel, all of them end to the same pixel due to the minimum pixel in the top row doesn't change. This image corresponds to a beat of a music file.

The readers can find a lot of examples in [2] and applications about seam-carving for images.

C. Onset Detection Segmentation

As we explained before, an onset detection algorithm is required if we need to keep the tempo of the song of music file we want to stretch. The time-scale algorithm doesn't need to calculate the tempo because it works with small windows (the length of these windows are too small than the tempo) and the seam-carving for spectrograms, by design, needs bigger windows, and a tempo preservation is needed. In [5] an implementation of an onset detection algorithm was presented, from [17]. Now, an

adaptation of this method, from [16] has been implemented. This implementation has become an additional work because we need a tempo detection algorithm which allows us determine the tempo in “real-time”. It means that our tempo detection algorithm needs to adapt the tempo in each region we consider in order to have, always, an attack at the beginning of each window. The onset detection algorithm in [17] doesn’t permit this adjustment of the tempo in each region, because it only calculates a constant tempo for all the audio file. Our onset detection algorithm works in this way. First, we calculate the tempo of the file in order to know the minimum space between one beat and the other. Then, we assume that not all the beats will snap with the tempo we have found. But we know that the tempo of a song, almost always, is constant during the song. Sometimes, there is a changes in the tempo, but always is a slow transition from the initial tempo to the end tempo. If a rapid transition of tempo is produced the user must segment these two regions as two different songs. Despite this infrequent case, we assume that the variation between beats due to a non constant tempo will be less than 10%. Usually is between 0 to 2%, because if not, then we perceive that the tempo of the song is not constant and we not consider this rhythm acceptable. So, once we have calculated the tempo of the file, we use a peak-picking algorithm says that the minimum distance between beats will be 90% of the original tempo. In this way, we assume that we will always find the beginning of the onset of every beat. Finally, an additional function has been added in order to segment each beat in as many regions as required, such eighth or sixteenth of the tempo. Also, we assume that the tempo between beats is constant.

In figure 10 there is a block diagram of this process.

Here there are some definitions that we must take into account when we design an onset detection algorithm. These concepts will be very useful when we design how to generate the gradient image from spectrogram images in order to stress the attacks and reduce the energy on the decay regions. It will be very important to get a gradient image showing these transitions with the maximum contrast as possible in order to maximize the energy map by finding low energy transients. See [16] for more detail.

Figure 10: Block diagram of the onset detection process. First we have a pre-processing to adapt the audio data to a standard audio data, then detect peaks and calculate the distance between peaks. That is a way to detect a tempo of an audio file.

Essentially, an onset detection is composed by 4 time regions of time well defined: attack, decay, sustain and release. These definitions are based on an electronic configurable keyboard [12], which has the ideal and unrealistic onset curve shape. If a musician plays an instrument can do these effects depending on the instrument. The fusion of these four parameters defines how an instrument is and how it has been played. These concepts can be extrapolated to a real instrument, too.

- Attack: When a note is played on an electronic keyboard the envelope is triggered. This means it starts rising from zero to the maximum value. How long this should take, depends on the Attack setting. If the Attack is set to "0", the maximum value is reached instantly. If this value is raised, it will take time before the maximum value is reached. See figure 11.

Figure 11: The upper image represents a common attack of any instrument. The bottom image represents the envelope of the upper image defining 4 perceptible areas of any attack.

- Decay: After the maximum value has been reached, the value starts to drop. How long this should take is governed by the Decay parameter.

If the reader wants to emulate the volume envelope of a note played on a piano, for example, the Attack should be set to "0" and the Decay parameter should be set to a medium value, so that the volume gradually decreases down to silence, even if the user keeps holding the key down. See figure 11.

- Sustain: The Sustain parameter determines the level the envelope should rest at, after the Decay. If the user sets Sustain to full level, the Decay setting has no effect since the volume of the sound is never lowered.

- Release: Finally, we have the Release parameter. This works just like the Decay parameter, except it determines the time it takes for the value to fall back to zero after releasing the key. See figure 11.

If the reader wants to emulate the volume envelope of an organ, he/she theoretically only really needs to use the Sustain parameter set to full level, as a basic organ volume envelope instantly goes to the maximum level (Attack "0") and stays there (Decay "0"), until the key is released and the sound instantly stops (Release "0").

But often a combination of Decay and Sustain is used to generate envelopes that rise up to the maximum value, then gradually decreases to finally land to rest on a level somewhere in-between zero and maximum. Note that Sustain represents a level, whereas the other envelope parameters represent times. See figure 11.

In [16] there are some onset detection techniques. According to [5], as we mentioned before, it has been selected for simply work and improvement of previous work. For this reason, here we review briefly this technique. For more detail, see [5]. This technique is a "Tempo and beat analysis of acoustical musical signals".

Essentially, figure 12 shows a six-band filter bank, which are of sixth-order elliptic filter with 3dB of ripple and 40dB of rejection and are inspired by psychoacoustic features. The cutoff frequencies of this bank filter are 200, 400, 800, 1600 and 3200Hz. See figure 13a. The input is filtered through each band and the output of each band will be processed separately by the same process. After this step, we are working with six channels, where each one contains information of a specific frequency band.

Figure 12: Bank filter of the sixth-order elliptic filters used when analyzing the peak-picking process.

The next step is to extract the envelope of each channel using a rectify-and-smooth method to filter each channel by a half-hanning window of 200ms and a cutoff frequency $f_c=10\text{Hz}$ over the envelope with -15dB response and 6dB/octava . It acts as a low pass filter. In figure 13b we see the shape of this window. The next step for each channel is to apply a differentiator and a half-wave rectifier. See figure 13c. The differentiator extracts fast transients (attacks) and ignore slow transients (release and sustain), which are not important for the onset detection. Then, we apply a half-wave rectifier in order to get the amplitude transient information as an absolute number for detecting peaks. Finally, we use a peak-picking algorithm in order to detect the distances between peaks. See figure 13d. This algorithm is very easy to implement, because the user defines some difference time between peaks. We use distances between 75 to 150 bpm. We can use other distances if we want, but this ones are de most used in commercial onset detection programs. Each time we detect a maximum in a region, we mark this position and find another maximum in the next region. In this way, we have many marks; all of them separated a distance between 75 to 150 bmp. Now we compute the differences between one to the other. If we compute a histogram of this distances, we will see that the most probability distance coincide with the tempo. See figure 13 to see how we calculate the tempo of the file, which is an improvement from [5] done for Seam Carving for Spectrograms application.

Figure 13a: output of the filter bank from [17].

Figure 13b: output of the half-hanning window, which acts as a rectify-and-smooth method.

Figure 13c: differentiator and half-wave rectifier.

Figure 13d: peak picking.

Finally, we must add that the tempo resolution of [5] is bigger than this new technique, but it is enough a low tempo resolution with $\pm 0.5\%$ BPM error. It only is needed in order to have an idea of the duration of the beat. Therefore, not high precision by detecting the tempo is required, because the temporal resolution of the spectrogram image is lower than this error. In addition, there is not error propagation due to a “real-time” tempo detection by determining the width of each spectrogram image. Remember that the window size the seam carving for spectrograms used is eighth, sixteenth or thirty-second of the tempo. User can define this parameter. See figure 14 and figure 15 for more details.

Figure 14: this picture shows the histogram of the distances between peaks detected. The most frequent distance corresponds to 100bpm. The other peak detected in 132bpm coincides with some percussion attacks, but with less energy (snare drum), while the 100bpm position coincides with the kick and bass, which have more energy.

Figure 15: block diagram of the filtering and peak-picking process in order to extract the tempo of the signal we want to compute. It is an adaptation from [5] in order to match the tempo in a faster way, but with less tempo resolution, which is enough for this application.

It is obvious that, in the same way that happens with all the onset detection algorithms, we need to analyze as maximum time as possible of the song for higher precision on matching de tempo. In this way, we worked for determining as maximum onsets as possible.

D. Adapting Seam Carving for Spectrograms

In this section, we describe the modifications applied to the original seam-carving algorithm in order to be used in a time-scaling application.

First, let us see a block diagram in figure 16 of all the process done from an audio file to the extraction of the time-scale factor envelope function. At the end, in the results section, we will compare many outputs of this system with the output of the Time-Scaling Algorithm [1].

It is important to be aware that this method might give us better results than previous algorithms, but might produce, also, non-desirable results. We will comment all the results in the conclusions section.

Figure 16 shows the steps taken in our method. This method was motivated after analyzing some artifacts with some kind of files using the original time-scale algorithm. These artifacts were an unreal sound when a slow attack was not detected due to slow but relevant transitions. If the reader expands to the maximum time-scale factor a sound without preserving the attack, a robotic sound due to the duplication of each frame of the sound is perceptible.

In order to avoid it, we must design an algorithm that is able to detect, not only fast attack or transitions, but also slow attacks and relevant transitions. If the reader analyzes an attack in the time domain, it is possible to see, periodically, a rapid growth of the amplitude, which coincides with the attack. If the reader divides the input file in region with some window length and use a little window (few times less than the beat region), probably the reader will be able to detect this window and compare it with others with slow transients and decide that the one with fast transients it the one that fits with the attack region. So, this window remain intact and we stretch the rest of the windows. If this attack is a slow transient and the reader uses little windows, he/she will be not able

to differentiate slow and fast transients, because all of them will be catalogued as slow transients, all these windows will behave as non-transients region, and a constant time-scale factor will be applied to all the windows, discarding attacks. The reader can solve it using a bigger window to analyze the audio signal, but this solution cannot be solved in time domain, to the amount of information in a big window for looking transients and the high probability error function.

Figure 16: block diagram of the fundamental steps of the seam carving for spectrograms process. First, we analyze the tempo of the input file. Then, we divide the input file in regions of sixteenth or thirty-second of the tempo (it depends on the rhythm of the music). Each region is analyzed, first, by computing the spectrogram, analyzing low energy region with the seam carving for spectrograms and extracting the histogram. Finally, each histogram is grouped as one big histogram and filtered becoming the time-scale factor envelope function. This function will be the input of the time-scale algorithm to define which time-scale factor must be applied to each region of the input file in order to get a stretched output file.

The seam carving for spectrograms algorithm could be a possible solution. This method uses bigger windows than the original time-scale algorithm (quarter, eighth, sixteenth or thirty-second of the tempo of the music file) when analyzing transients and use the spectrogram information for looking transients. The Seam-Carving algorithm generates a horizontal gradient image from the spectrogram in order to detect vertical transients (see figure 8). All the variations in the vertical dimension over this gradient image will be computed to generates the energy map, which increase the energy when detects high energy regions in the gradient image.

It means that this algorithm will detect low energy regions as regions without transitions in the vertical dimension over the gradient image and will detect high energy regions as regions with transitions.

The horizontal direction represents the time along this image, and this dimension is not relevant for this application. For example, a long sustained note can be time-scaled without artifacts. However, the vertical gradient will be high near to the harmonic partials.

Let us see an example of the attack information contained in a spectrogram image in order to be aware that this onset is more perceptible in a spectrogram than the waveform. In figure 17a we see that there are two perceptible onsets, one at the beginning of the first region, and the other at the beginning of the sixth region. Nevertheless, if we see the spectrogram representation of this waveform, in figure 17b, we see that in this spectrogram appears more than two onsets.

We see in the spectrogram, easily, three onsets, which coincide with the three instruments contained in this region of music file. It means that, if we are analyzing the waveform in terms of variation of amplitude without filtering, there are some instruments that are not perceptible. In contrary, with the spectrogram, we see all this variation in the same image. That is because, usually, an attack is when there is an increment of almost all the frequencies in the spectrogram in the same time, and it appears over the spectrogram as a peak of energy at a moment. That is what we need in order to run the seam carving for spectrograms. Therefore, this algorithm must be able to detect the same or more onsets than us when we are looking for this spectrogram.

These arguments were the premise to initiate this process, which will be described in detail in the following lines.

Figure 17a: waveform of a rhythm music file where we see 2 onsets, one at the beginning and the other at the beginning of the 6th region.

Figure 17b: spectrogram of the figure 13a waveform. In this spectrogram we can see easily that we don't have 2 onsets, we have 3 onsets and we see it easily because we are looking the vertical energy along the time, and the attack is the positive gradient transition, when we are in a low energy region and immediately we pass to a high energy region in almost all frequencies. This transition is considered as an attack. This spectrogram is a 600ms sound, corresponding to a beat of a song and these features for spectrogram: window length=1024, overlapping=1/32, zero padding=2.

The Seam-Carving for Spectrograms algorithm starts by loading a music file, converting it into a mono file and resampling it with a maximum frequency sampling of 22050Hz. Then, we must detect the tempo in the way we have described in section IV-C. Next step is to decide which parameters of window length, zero padding and overlapping we must use in order to get useful spectrograms. We must take into account that, as we said before, we need high resolution in time in order to obtain as many seams as possible in only a thirty-second region of the tempo (50ms with a song of 150bpm, the maximum bpm by design).

It means that the overlapping must be very little and the window size not so big. While we are considering time resolution, the frequency resolution must be enough to perceive the most important transitions in the frequency domain. A logarithmic frequency representation was considered as an input of the time scaling, but then, as high frequencies are very important for every onset, with a logarithmic representation it

reduces the area in the spectrogram. A lineal frequency representation is the best way to have resolution in high and low frequencies. That is the reason that we use little values for zero padding, which are enough to have frequency resolution and very little values for the overlapping in order to increase the time resolution. We have run the system with the following parameters

- window length: from 256 to 1024 samplers
- overlapping: from 1/16 to 1/64
- zero padding=2

As we see in figure 14, once we have the tempo of the file, an approximation of the exact tempo (not high precision in matching the tempo is required, because it's only a reference in order to divide the file in little regions) we divide the input file in as many region as the division region we want (usually a region of the sixteenth of the tempo) over the duration file. Our algorithm will compute all this regions as independent windows and, at the end, we will combine all these windows in one curve. Therefore, each region will be the input of our spectrogram process unit in order to get the image that will be the input of the seam carving for spectrograms. This image will have as many rows as the FFT resolution (window length) and as many columns as windows will return the spectrogram process unit with the frames there are in one-sixteenth region of the tempo. This temporal resolution will be determined by the previous parameters for the spectrogram, like overlapping.

The seam carving for spectrograms main unit will compute every spectrogram as an image and the number of returned seams will depend on the time-scale factor. For example, if we choose a time-scale=2 or 0.5, we will find half seams as columns has the spectrogram. It will be the maximum number of seams we will find in a spectrogram.

Let us see in figure 18 all the process done for searching the seams.

1) Sobel Operator Filtering

As we see in figure 18, once we have the spectrogram image, we must calculate the horizontal gradient image. The gradient operator used is the Sobel gradient. The Sobel

Operator is used as edge detection in image processing, computing the gradient of the image intensity function. Depending on the size of the Sobel Matrix, the thickness of the edges varies. The original Seam Carving algorithm uses a 3x3 Sobel matrix. In our case, we cannot use this matrix size because we do not want to analyze thin edges on the spectrogram. After many experiments, we have decided to use a matrix bigger than 3x3. Considering it, what we want to get is an energy map which shows us high energy regions for the attacks and low energy regions for releases. It means that the contrast between both regions must be maximized. Also, using big matrix we avoid low energy regions in the energy map between the beginning and the end of the attack. The Sobel Matrix size depends on the number of columns of the spectrogram image, which depends on the overlapping. The user must decide the length of this Sobel Matrix in order to avoid artifacts when many transitions are close.

Figure 18: Block Diagram of the seam carving for spectro-grams. It begins with a spectrogram of a region and ends with a stretched spectrogram of this region.

Let us make a study of what happens with an ideal spectrogram and the Sobel Matrix, which shows three attacks, like the ones in figure 17b, but only with the transition region, what would be the ideal representation of a gradient for our energy map.

In figure 19a we see, in white, the attack and the duration of the transient region, high energy, and in black the rest of the signal. When we apply the Sobel operator on the spectrogram, we obtain the horizontal gradient (figure 19b). The vertical gradient is discarded because does not give us useful information about the transients, only frequency information, and that is not our aim.

Figure 19a: ideal spectrogram, with the same transients as we see in figure 17b in order to compute an ideal gradient and energy map from a spectrogram.

Figure 19b: horizontal gradient of figure 19a. A 3x3 Sobel matrix operator has been applied over horizontal dimension, which coincides with time dimension, in order to show us transitions over time.

Figure 19c: resulting energy map from figure 19b. The seams will pass only over these 6 low energy regions of this figure.

We see in figure 19b how the transitions between black and white and vice versa on figure 19a are represented with a vertical line, which has the same width as Sobel Matrix. In this case, 3x3. It means that if we have three instruments in our spectrogram, we get six transients, two for each instrument. It means that the Sobel operator give us a low energy region while the transient occurs on the spectrogram. It is an undesirable effect. Then, the energy map, figure 19c, computes high and low energy regions on the

gradient. The representation of the energy map is almost the same in this case because we only have two levels of energy. As the reader can imagine, with this energy map representation, the seams will pass through the energy map between 6 regions, the ones that fit with the transient on the spectrogram and the other regions, that fit with low energy regions on the spectrogram. This result ends by applying a time-scale factor on undesirable region. That is what we do not want for our system. We would like to preserve the transient regions. In other words, in this case we would like that the energy map was identical of this ideal spectrogram. In this case, all the seams will be founded only over low energy regions of the energy. One solution we propose is to increase the size of the Sobel matrix, in order to reduce the length the vertical lines on the gradient between the beginning of the transient on the spectrogram and the end of this transient.

Figure 20 show us the same as figure 19, but now with a Sobel matrix with a size of 17x17. This representation show us how the energy map show us the hi-hat and the snare drum as regions with high energy and the kick as two thin regions. About the kick, that is because there is no transitions close to the kick drum. That is another undesirable effect. On the other hand, between the hi-hat and the snare drum there is a thin low region that produces a segmentation of these two instruments on the energy map. The length of each line in the gradient image is now of 17 pixels. In an easy way, the reader can imagine that if the Sobel matrix size is bigger that the minimum distances between transients in the spectrogram, no low energy region is detected. Therefore, that is the trade off between a little Sobel matrix and a bigger one. The user can choose this parameter, depending on the duration of the attacks the user's audio file has.

Computing the spectrogram on figure 17b with a 3x3 Sobel Matrix we obtain figure 21. In figure 21, we see how on the energy map (figure 21c) the seams will pass, first, over the transients on the spectrogram, the hi-hat and the snare. That is contrary of what we want. That is because now the Sobel Operator acts as edge detection, and obviously, the transitions on the gradient image are over the transients on the spectrogram. If we increase the Sobel matrix size to 17x17, as we do in figure 20, we obtain figure 22. In figure 22, we appreciate, from the energy map (figure 22c), that the lowest energy region coincides with the low energy region on the spectrogram (figure 22a). That is a desirable effect. Despite of it, low energy regions over the hi-hat and the snare drum are

a little bit confused. However, the result we obtain show us how almost all the seams pass over the low energy region between the kick and the other instruments. Nevertheless, we cannot use this time region because it coincides with a beat, and the output will change the rhythm. We must use eighth or sixteenth time region for our computation, depending on the region.

Figure 20a: ideal spectrogram, with the same transients as we see in figure 17b in order to compute an ideal gradient and energy map from a spectrogram.

Figure 20b: horizontal gradient of figure 20a. A 17×17 Sobel matrix operator has been applied over horizontal dimension.

Figure 20c: resulting energy map from figure 20b. The seams will pass only over these 5 low energy regions of this figure.

Figure 21a: the same spectrogram used in figure 17b.

Figure 21b: horizontal gradient of figure 21a. A 3×3 Sobel matrix operator has been applied over horizontal dimension.

Figure 21c: resulting energy map from figure 21b. The seams will pass only over lowest energy regions of this figure.

2) Wavelet Filtering

Before we see the results with this proposed time segmentation, let us see how we can maximize our results by filtering the spectrogram, with the Matlab Wavelet Tool.

Figure 22a: the same spectrogram used in figure 17b.

Figure 22b: horizontal gradient of figure 22a. A 17×17 Sobel matrix operator has been applied over horizontal dimension.

Figure 22c: resulting energy map from figure 22b. The seams will pass only over lowest energy regions of this figure, which coincides with the time region between the kick and hi-hat and some low energy regions over the hi-hat and the snare drum.

Figure 23 shows the low pass filter image of the spectrogram, the high pass filter image and the vertical and horizontal frequencies. We see how the low pass filter image has less noise on the low energy regions. It will be better for our gradient representation, allowing the energy map fits better with our ideal aim.

In figure 24b we see how there is less noise than figure 24a. The contrast between low and high energy regions is higher, and it produces better results with any image processing technique. In our final implementation, we will use low pass filtered images, resulting from the wavelet analysis.

And finally, before analyzing the steps after the energy map, let us see how figure 25 show us a cleaner version of the energy map (figure 25c) with a filtered spectrogram (figure 25a) than figure 22. In this case, we have more contrast between low and high

energy regions.

Once we have the energy map, we must search for the seams over low energy regions. In this step, another adaptation from the original Seam Carving algorithm was required. Be aware how the original Seam Carving algorithm searches for lowest energy paths over the vertical dimension. See figure 26. This seam is not vertical 100%, because when searching for the minimum energy path in the top-down direction tends to navigate from one column to another. It means that we can remove the pixels selected for the next energy map but we cannot remove this region from the original audio file, because which frame are we deleting?

Figure 23a: Low pass filter of the spectrogram in 17b.

Figure 23b: high pass filter of figure 17b

Figure 23c: Horizontal components of figure 17b

Figure 23d: Vertical components of figure 17b.

Figure 24a: The same spectrogram as in 17b.

Figure 24b: Low pass filter of the spectrogram in 24a.

Figure 25a: the same spectrogram used in figure 24b.

Figure 25b: horizontal gradient of figure 25a. A 7x7 Sobel matrix operator has been applied over horizontal dimension.

Figure 25c: resulting energy map from figure 25b. The seams will pass only over lowest energy regions of this figure. Image contrast on figure 25c is bigger than figure 22c.

Figure 26: this figure shows us how the seam passes over the minimum energy path in the vertical dimension. The top image represents the seam over the energy map and the bottom image the same seam over the spectrogram. We can see with this image that the first seam to remove coincides with the most irrelevant region of the spectrogram, and that is the most irrelevant region of this audio file. This seam is the one we delete from the spectrogram image in order to calculate the next energy map for the next seam.

The solution to this problem is to choose only one column of the ones the seam passes through. We know that all the attacks have a rapid increment of energy when it begins, and it decays until it disappears. It means that we prefer to choose the left side of this vertical seam instead of the right side. However, it produces that many vertical seams pass over the same column. Therefore, the best solution is to calculate the mean column value and choose the left side of this vertical seam. See Figure 27. In this way, this seam represents a region of the audio file and we can compute it. It, also, increments the probability of deleting different columns and not almost always the same column in comparison with the other method described above. Nevertheless, the reader must take into account that instead of we are choosing a column to delete in the spectrogram, we cannot delete from the spectrogram image this vertical seam. We must

delete the original low energy path searched for the seam carving algorithm in order to calculate the next energy map (the seam showed in figure 26), because if not we are not maintaining the content of the spectrogram and it produces that many seams pass over the same path and they are not relatively uniform over the spectrogram.

Deleting many seams of the spectrogram with the seam carving for spectrograms produces an effect that the beginning of the attack is always preserved and the decay region is removed. That is what we are looking in this adaptation of the seam carving algorithm.

Figure 27: the top image represents the vertical seam over the energy map and the bottom image the vertical seam over the spectrogram image. This representation is only for showing that this seam or column or time region is the one we consider for determining the time-scaling factor envelope.

In order to understand better this process, imagine that we only want to delete one seam and it represents to delete a region or beat frame of the music file. If this seam is vertical, we can remove easily this region from the original music file. In terms of the time-scale algorithm, this operation is to stretch this region and the contiguous of this

region in order to reduce the artifacts when computing the time-scale algorithm. However, if we try to delete the lowest energy path found by seam carving algorithm, this operation will not be possible.

In few words, when we run the seam carving for spectrograms algorithm after analyzing a spectrogram, it returns a seam over the vertical dimension. The position of the seam over the spectrogram corresponds to a column number, and this position is stored in a buffer in order to design, at the end of this preliminary process, the histogram of the removed columns.

This process begins with the first window or region of a music file and ends when the removed seams coincide with the number of seams we want to remove according to the time-scale factor applied by the user. When the spectrogram has the new size, we have in a buffer all the columns we have removed. Now, we must sort all this seams according the position in the buffer. We mean that, for example, in the first iteration we remove the column 50 of 100, and the next removed seam is on column 25, the second column is in the 25th position. Nevertheless, if the second column removed is in the 75th position, then we must take into account that this column is not the 75th, so it is in the 76th position because before we removed a column in a lower position. In this case, we must increase the column positing by one. For the third column to remove we must make the same process.

Summarizing, when we remove a column we must search for the columns removed before with a smaller position in comparison with current column we are removing and adding to this column as many columns it is necessary. Figure 28 shows the algorithm applied for this buffer.

```
function out=ordenacio_seams(in);
for i=1:length(in)
    if i==1
        outtemp(i)=in(i);
    else
        outtemp(i)=in(i)+length(find(in(1:i)<in(i)));
    end
end
out=sort(outtemp);
```

Figure 28: algorithm used by sorting the buffer of the seams removed in every window. The buffer 'in' is the unsorted one and the 'out' is the sorted buffer of the seams removed.

The operation described in figure 28 generates the histogram. With the sorted buffer, we know how many columns we have removed from the original spectrogram and their position. The mean of this histogram, computed for each window or region, coincides with the time-scale factor we want to apply to the entire file.

Nevertheless, we cannot use this histogram, because there are many abrupt slopes, which will produce artifacts when the time-scale algorithm works. See figure 29. One solution is to apply a low pass filter to this histogram in order to get a smooth curve and avoid artifacts when there are high transitions between low time-scale factors and high time-scale factors in a little region. See figure 30 and figure 31. We have detected that after apply the filter, the mean of the histogram tends to be less than the time-scale factor desired but very close to it. One easy solution is to increment the time-scale factor with some value in the regions that the time-scale factor is more than 1 and the rest of the histogram remain the time-scale factor to the neutral value, because in these region we don't want to apply any compression/expansion. One easy way to procedure is looking for a value that makes the mean of the filtered histogram equal with the one we want when it is elevated to the histogram mean.

When we are in this point, we only need to mix the histogram extracted from each window and make a new one, which represents all the seams removed of the audio file we are computing. All individual histograms have the same time-scale factor as a mean and the final histogram has the desired time-scale factor as a mean.

See in figure 32a how is the filtered histogram different in comparison with the one in figure 32b which is a non-filtered histogram. Figure 32b corresponds with the removed seams from the spectrogram. The figure 32a corresponds with the applied curve to the time-scale algorithm. Also, see how the ratio between the highest time-scale factor and the lowest time-scale factor in figure 32a is lower than in figure 32b. This little ratio is desired in order to avoid artifacts for high transients in the time-scale factor in little regions.

Before explaining how to use this histogram for the time-scale algorithm, let us see the shape of a window of this histogram and, finally, the completely histogram. See in figure 29 the resulting histogram from the spectrogram above. The reader can see that the seams are concentrated on low energy regions and there are no seams over high

energy regions. Then, in figure 30, we show how this histogram fits well with what we would like to compress/expand manually if we would use the entire sound we are using, which is four beats of sound and a time segmentation of sixteenth time of the tempo. We mean that the highest factors coincide with the lowest energy regions in the spectrogram. That is what we were looking for! In figure 31, we see the same in figure 30, but with an eighth beat for the analysis. If the reader listens to this result, the attack preserving region is better than using a sixteenth of the beat, but then there are changes in the rhythm in some regions and that is something that we must avoid. For this reason, the user must decide which regions need eighth or sixteenth, in order to get the better results without changes in the rhythm. We will analyze it in the results section.

Figure 29: This figure shows the spectrogram for a half beat window length and the corresponding not-filtered histogram founded for this region. We can see that the low energy regions have bigger time-scale factor than the high energy regions, like attacks.

Figure 30: The histogram fits well with what we would like to compress/expand manually. Remember that the neutral time-scale factor is 1. If time-scale factor > 1 we are expanding, and we compress in the other way. This image corresponds to sixteenth beat for the analysis. Now, the quality of the sound and the final result are what we were expecting for, but the graphical resolution produces some difficulties to see, in comparison with figure 31. The y axis of the filtered histogram corresponds to the time-scale factor.

E. Generating Time-Scaling Factor Envelope

That is the last step of our system. We must adapt the generated histogram from the seam carving for spectrograms to the input parameters of the time-scale algorithm. It is as easy as generate a txt file containing all the different regions contained in the time-scale factor envelope curve. It means that when there is no changes of the time-scale factor, this regions remain a constant value from the beginning to the end of this region. When there is some constant positive/negative slope, we write the initial value and the end value for this region. Therefore, each region corresponds with a region of the music file where there is not changes in the slope. When the slope changes, a new region is

defined. Figure 33 shows an example of this text file, where the first row is the defined regions and the second row shows the beginning and the end of each region and the time-scale factor at the beginning and at the end of this region.

Now, we are prepared to transform all the music files we want, because we have an algorithm that is able to detect the attack and release regions of any music file and then generate the time-scale factor envelope function in order to be processed with the time-scale algorithm.

Finally, the user can segment any audio file and choose the time-scale factor he/she wants to apply to any segment.

Figure 31: The histogram fits well with what we would like to compress/expand manually. Remember that the neutral time-scale factor is 1. If time-scale factor > 1 we are expanding, and we compress in the other way. This image corresponds to half beat for the analysis due to a better resolution. It produces changes in the rhythm, despite of a better quality sound of the instruments. See how in figure 30 the shape of the time-scale factor envelope curve seems like a zigzag curve, where the neutral time-scale factor coincide, almost always, with the beginning of the window, where there is the attack, and higher time-scale factors are applied in the rest regions. In contrast with figure 31, here we see how high time-scale factors coincide with the rhythm of the music file. In figure 31, we see a patron which coincides with the patron of the music file. But as we said before, this implementation changes the rhythm.

Figure 32a (black plot): low pass filtered histogram. This histogram is useful for generate the text file for the time-scale algorithm. The mean needs a correction factor in order to get the exact value. Also, see how the ratio between the highest time-scale factor and the lowest time-scale factor in figure 27a is lower than figure 27b. It avoid many artifacts due to fast transitions of the time-scale factor in a little region.
 Figure 32b (red plot): non-filtered histogram. It is not useful for generate the text file for time-scale algorithm. The natural mean of this histogram coincides with the desired time-scale factor.

2794
0.0000 1.0000 0.0501 1.0000 0.0501 1.1010 0.0515 1.1010 0.0515 1.1010 0.0523 1.3033 ... 0.9950
1.2021 0.9957 1.1010 0.9957 1.1010 0.9964 1.0000 0.9964 1.0000 1.0000 1.0000

Figure 33: here we see the aspect of the time-scaling factor envelope function in a text file. The first row is the defined regions and the second row shows the beginning and the end of each region and the time-scale factor at the beginning and at the end of this region.

V. RESULTS

We have generated several audio files in order to compare these results with the current time-scale algorithm. Unfortunately, no analytical way exists to evaluate the improvements of this system, we describe in this section the impressions of the experts after comparing several audio files between the original sound and the transformed one with the current time-scale algorithm and the new one using the Seam Carving for Spectrograms.

The experiment was carried out in the following way. First, each expert listens to the original sound. Then, they listen to the output of some time-scale factor (usually this factor was 2 because is the time-scale factor that produces more artifacts, lower time scale factors than 1 does not present almost any differences between both methods) and detect artifacts in comparison with the original sound. Finally, they listen to the output of our system and compare the regions where there were artifacts with the current time scale algorithm with our system. The results can be summarized as follows:

- Usually, the transient is preserved in our system in comparison with the current time scale algorithm. It has been approved by comparing the transient between the original sound and the output of the time-scale algorithm.
- Sometimes, the attack is not well detected and the artifacts seem the same with both methods. No improvements they detect. We must take into account that the time scale algorithm is always working instead of having an external time-scale factor envelope function. It means that no worse results we will obtain.
- Due to the preservation of the transient with a time scale factor close to 1, the rest part of the region we are computing has a bigger time scale factor, far from 1. It produces an expected sensation where the musician seems to get lost with the music score he/she is playing. Despite of these effects, the sound is good.
- When we use big windows for segmentation, like beat or eighth duration of the tempo, the rhythm tends to change. We have explained this effect above. However, the experts appreciate how the transitions do not present artifacts. In other words, sometimes, the artifacts are less notable than the current time scale algorithm. It is an expected result.

- When we use small windows for segmentation, like sixteenth duration of the tempo or less, the rhythm does not change but the transient preservation is not well computed. For example, if the reader sees the two first spectrogram windows in figure 30, the first one seems to be only an attack shape, while the second window seems to be a release shape. It means that if we are looking for low energy regions in both windows, in the first window the algorithm is not able to find almost any low energy region and tends to concentrate the seams at the end because the highest energy of the transient is at the beginning, but there are no high contrast between low and high energy regions. Nevertheless, in the second window, despite of higher energy at the beginning than the end, no high-energy regions are found. The wanted effect is not to remove some seams from the transient and others from the release region. What we expect is to remove only the release region. It only is possible if we use windows combining each transient of the audio file with its release. It means that the user must segment manually the audio file if he/she wants to get the best results. If not, an improvement is appreciated with this features, but the reader can get better results with a custom segmentation.
- The window size of the FFT allows more precision when this value is big, because when we are looking for seams over the energy map, the mean of the seam fits better with the desirable seam we would like to remove manually.
- The overlapping defines the temporal resolution of the spectrogram and the energy map. If this resolution is not so big, the precision of the seams is poor and high time-scale factor is applied over each seam. It produces abrupt changes resulting in a non-smooth time scale factor envelope. On the other hand, if we use a little value for the overlapping, many seams will be removed from the energy map, creating a good sound due to a smooth time scale factor envelope. However, the probability of deleting seams from transient regions is bigger. As little overlapping value is, more close is the window size we are using than the time scale algorithm. It means that very small values will never give us better results. The user must be aware of the trade off between little and big values for the overlapping.
- The user can decide for the Sobel matrix size. Small values produces undesirable effects, because acts as an edge detector. Bigger values delete thin low energy

regions on the spectrogram. A trade off must be present when decide this value.

Finally, our conclusion is that if the user chooses appropriate values of tempo segmentation, overlapping, window size for the FFT and Sobel matrix size we get less artifacts than the current time-scale algorithm. Concerning the onset detector, one might consider to use a user-supervised segmentation, which would improve the sound quality results.

On the next section, we explain all the improvements and future work for this system.

VI. DISCUSSION

At the beginning of this project, we thought that we would only need some modifications of the seam carving algorithm, we could use a standard onset detection algorithm and segment our audio file as many beats it has and would get good results. After the first experiments, we realized that we needed to change many features of the seam carving algorithm, described above, design a new onset detection in order to fit with what we need and segment the audio file in a custom way. Then, we had to design a new way to get and sort the seams removed by seam carving algorithm in order to generate a histogram and generate automatically an output useful for the time-scale algorithm. All these steps are described in this project.

For future improvements, a new way to generate the horizontal gradient is needed instead of an edge detector, like Sobel Operator. A new gradient method is required in order to obtain an energy map that fits better with the spectrogram and preserve the transient regions and reduce the release regions. In this way, bigger values for overlapping could work in order to reduce the computational cost of any CPU.

An improvement of the current onset detection should be considered. Now, the current onset detection algorithm uses 0 phase at the beginning of each beat. It means that it adjusts the tempo in every beat. What we have observed the need of short time periods during the beat (eighth, sixteenth duration of the beat) and we must generate an onset detection algorithm which is able to adjust, not only the beat phase, but also the internal beat phase. It means that this algorithm must segment each beat period in as many transients it has (one, two, three...) and adjusts the phase for each transient. In this way, the user doesn't need to segment manually the audio file.

Finally, the results of this Master Thesis will be available on the MTG web site (<http://mtg.upf.edu>), including the audio examples used for evaluation.

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